

Supplementary Online Material (SOM):

The dawn of the Middle Paleolithic in Atapuerca: The lithic assemblage of TD10.1 from Gran Dolina

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SOM S1

The Gran Dolina site: Paleoenvironmental approaches

The sedimentary, biostratigraphic, and palynological data show small changes in the paleoenvironmental conditions through the TD10.1 sequence. In the lowermost subunit (TD10.4) milder and more humid conditions give way to progressively drier and colder ones, marked by the predominance of Poaceae and fewer Mediterranean taxa in TD10.3. In TD10.2 climate amelioration is represented by recuperation of the Mediterranean component of the flora, which is later consolidated during TD10.1, with a greater abundance of mesothermic taxa (García-Antón and Sainz-Ollero, 1991; Mallol and Carbonell, 2008; Blain et al., 2009, 2015; Cuenca-Bescós et al., 2011; Rodríguez et al., 2011; Campaña et al., 2017; Vallverdú i Poch, 2017). The TD10 faunal assemblages are related to Faunal Unit 6 (FU6), the latest of the Sierra de Atapuerca sites. The macromammal community points to an open savannah, but micromammal and herpetofaunal studies also reveal the existence of an open, moist habitat, complemented with forested and wet areas (Blain et al., 2008, 2009; Rodríguez et al., 2011; Cuenca-Bescós et al., 2016).

SOM S2

Knapping methods description

The knapping or exploitation methods considered here can be summarized as follows:

- Unipolar longitudinal: Knapping is typically done on a single surface, and the flake scars run unidirectionally along the thickness of the blank using either cortical or non-cortical surfaces. This method is essentially applied to pebbles and cobbles.
- Centripetal: Either unifacial or bifacial, although the latter predominates. It involves recurrent knapping around the edge of a blank. When this method is bifacial, the angles, alternation of striking surfaces, and relationship between the faces are considered to define specific flaking methods. We must bear in mind the variability in centripetal, peripheral, and discoidal flaking methods (Mourre, 2003; Terradas, 2003; de la Torre, 2011). Discoidal cores feature secant faces that work alternatively as preparation and exploitation surfaces. In these cases, volume control of the flaking surfaces through cordal removals is seen (Boëda, 1993). In other cases, centripetal cores show hierarchized flaking surfaces, the flattest working as the main flaking surface and the other used as a striking platform prepared using short, abrupt removals. We consider the Levallois

method to be the extreme and most complex expression of this hierarchy. In our study, only when there was a certain volumetric control of surfaces (lateral and distal convexities), preparation/shaping of the striking platforms, and predetermination of the final products pursued, were cores ascribed to the Levallois method (Boëda, 1994).

- **Orthogonal:** This method involves bifacial and trifacial strategies applying a bidirectional or opposed series of removals on the flaking surfaces. The multifacial multipolar strategy is based on the continuous creation of surfaces by rotating the core, which is used as both a striking and detachment platform. The angles between these surfaces tend to be close to 90° (orthogonal).
- **Other:** In some cases, usually when cores are in the very initial or final stages of their reduction sequences (i.e., test-cores, exhausted cores, etc.), the knapping method applied cannot be inferred. In those cases, cores are ascribed to this category.

SOM S3

Raw material resources at Sierra de Atapuerca

One of the most important characteristics of the Sierra de Atapuerca environment is its wealth of biotic and abiotic resources. Its varied geological context offers a wide variety of lithic resources in the vicinities of the sites, rarely more than 4 km distant (García-Antón and Mallol, 1998; Mallol, 1999; García-Antón Trassierra and Mosquera, 2007; García-Antón, 2010; Ollé et al., 2013). Only two elements, made from Arlanzón chert and Villagonzalo-Pedernales chert, come from more remote outcrops, located between 7 and 18 km away.

Atapuerca is located between the Tertiary Duero Basin and, to the S-SE, the Paleozoic foothills of the Sistema Central. Between these are the Mesozoic formations that make up the Sierra de Atapuerca itself (Pineda, 1997; Benito-Calvo and Pérez-González, 2007). This results in a wide variety of potential raw material resources, each providing different knapping qualities and functional possibilities (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2017).

Two different Cretaceous chert outcrops are located in the karren area of the upper part of the Sierra, part of the Turonian-Lower Santonian formation: 1) the Rasa de San Vicente Area, yielding nodules up to 15 cm long (this is the best-represented variety in the archeological record); and 2) Valdecuende, with smaller nodules, rarely exceeding 10 cm in length. This is a good quality raw material, but the uneven presence of inner flaws

and irregularities, as well its reduced size, may condition its workability (Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2014).

Neogene chert is related to the Astaracian marl limestone formation. Large blocks of this raw material (usually more than 1 m long) are found on the erosional surfaces of these Neogene limestones. The outcrops are located at both the W-NW and E-SE margins of the Sierra. This raw material has also been recorded in subprimary and secondary deposits (Navazo et al., 2008). Its abundance in the vicinities of the site and the large size of the available blocks resulted in it being the most frequent raw material type in the Atapuerca archeological records. In contrast, its quality varies from block to block, and even within a block (i.e., irregular texture, presence of geodes, internal flaws, surface alteration), which may influence its workability.

The Cambrian, Ordovician, and Carboniferous materials from the primary Sierra de la Demanda formations are available from the Quaternary deposits of the two main rivers: the Arlanzón, to the south; and the Vena, to the north. The Arlanzón river has a sequence of 14 Lower and Middle Pleistocene terraces, located 0.5–1.5 km to the Sierra de Atapuerca sites (Benito-Calvo and Pérez-González, 2007, 2015). The ESR-OB dating series relates the T7_{AZN} +38-42 and T8_{AZN} +26-35 fluvial terraces with the TD10 deposits (400 ± 90 ka and 370 ± 70 ka; Moreno et al., 2012). The Arlanzón terraces were the preferential procurement location for sandstones and medium and coarse-grained quartzites of suitable size and morphology for the shaping of large tools, as well as cobbles for percussive uses (García-Antón, 2010, 2016).

Finally, the Arenas de Utrillas Facies is an Early Cambrian detrital formation containing quartzitic conglomerates (Pineda, 1997). The outcrops are located 4.8 km to the NE of Gran Dolina. It contains high quality metaquartzite, orthoquartzite, and quartz. The quartzite is defined by its fine-grained granulometry and excellent conchoidal fracture, although medium-grained quartzites are also present. Nevertheless, the high incidence of internal flaws in some cobbles hinders its workability. Quartz pebbles are quite abundant and defined by their high functional and knapping quality (NS group) and scarce (or absent) internal flaws (NN group). This conglomeratic formation is partially eroded by the Vena river, the terraces of which yield quartzite and quartz pebbles.

Limestone cobbles are available in the immediate vicinity of the site, in Pico stream and some fossilised river channels, but these played a restricted role in the lithic production strategies of the TD10.1 assemblages.

SOM Figure S1. Histogram of the lithic processes represented in the TD10.1 assemblages according to the lithic categories.

SOM Figure S2. Scatter plot of the length and width of the unknapped pebbles and cobbles. Abbreviations: Bna = without evident percussion marks; Bnb = hammerstones; Bnc = broken cobbles/ hammerstones. Confidence ellipsoids interval = 90%.

SOM Figure S3. Histogram of the knapping methods according to number of cores identified in the TD10.1 lithic assemblages.

SOM Figure S4. A) Box-and-whisker plots with the dimensional features of the cores from Lower TD10.1. B) Mean number of scars on the preferential flaking surface (C1) and secondary flaking surface (C2) of the cores from Lower TD10.1. Horizontal lines represent median values, boxes second and third quartiles, whiskers maximum and minimum values up to 1.5 interquartile range, and dots are outliers.

SOM Figure S5. Histogram of the number of scars on dorsal faces according to the lithic assemblages. B) Histogram of the dorsal corticality of flakes. C) Histogram of the striking platform types. D) Box-and-whisker plots of butt thickness and area of the complete flakes from Lower TD10.1. E) Box-and-whisker plots of butt thickness and area of the

complete flakes from Upper TD10.1-A. Horizontal lines represent median values, boxes second and third quartiles, whiskers maximum and minimum values up to 1.5 interquartile range, and dots are outliers. Abbreviations: CO = cortical; CO(NCO) = predominately cortical; NCO(CO) = predominately non-cortical; NCO = non-cortical; NF: non-faceted; UF = unifaceted; BF = bifaceted; MF = multifaceted.

SOM Figure S6. Densities plots of the length of the retouched flakes from Lower TD10.1 and Upper TD10.1-A (excluding large cutting tools).

SOM Figure S7. Scatter plot of the length and width (mm) of the hammerstones and the knapped elements recycled as percussive elements from the Lower TD10.1 assemblage. Confidence ellipsoids interval = 80%.

A)

B)

SOM Figure S8. A) Correspondence analysis plot of the exploitation methods (in red) and raw material varieties (in blue) from Lower TD10.1 assemblage ($\chi^2 = 72.009$, $df = 40$; $p < 0.001$); dimensions 1 and 2 explain 81% of the inertia. B) Correspondence analysis

plot considering the lithic assemblages of Lower TD10.1 and Upper TD10.1-A as a whole ($\chi^2 = 78.23$, $df = 40$, $p = < 0.001$); dimensions 1 and 2 explain 71% of the inertia. Abbreviations: QT_FG = fine-grained quartzite; QT_MG = medium-grained quartzite; QT_CG = coarse-grained quartzite; QT_Indet = indeterminate type of quartzite; QZ_NY = quartz of morphostructural group NY; QZ_YN = quartz of morphostructural group YN.

SOM Table S1

Archeostratigraphic units, occupational models and main technological features identified in the archeological levels of TD10.1 subunit.

Archeological level	Number of artifacts	Archeostratigraphic units ^a	Thickness of the Archeostratigraphic units ^a	Type of occupation	Technological features
Upper TD10.1-A	729	TD10.1 a-c	30–50 cm	Sporadic and short-termed occupations	Lithic recycling, Levallois flakes, Expedient technology, Scarce LCT
Upper TD10.1-B	138	TD10.1 d-e	10–40 cm	Short-termed occupations	Expedient technology
Lower TD10.1.	21,522	TD10.1 f-g	30–55 cm	Micropalimpsest. Residential and short-termed occupation	Lithic recycling, bone retouchers, Bone industry, Levallois and discoidal cores, Scarce LCT, Tool-kit diversification
		TD10.1 h (bone-bed level)	10–20 cm	Micropalimpsest. Residential occupations.	Lithic recycling, bone retouchers, Levallois and discoidal cores. Composite tools., Scarce LCT. Tool-kit diversification

^a According to Obregón (2012).

SOM Table S2

Univariate analysis (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test) of the Lower TD10.1 cores according to their metric data, raw material and methods.

		Length	Width	Thickness
Raw material	D	24.288	23.625	21.96
	df	4	4	4
	p	6,99E-05	9,49E-05	2,04E-04
Method	D	19.934	15.428	13.447
	df	5	5	5
	p	0.001286	8.68E-03	0.01953

SOM Table S3

Metric features of the complete flakes from Lower TD10.1 and Upper TD10.1-A

		L. TD10.1			Upper TD10.1-A		
		Length	Width	Thickness	Length	Width	Thickness
Sandstone	Mean	15.68	16.5	4.86	22,29	25,71	8,823
	SD	11.608	12.565	3.993	12.01	16.56	7.31
	IQR	11	13	4	14	28	7
	CV	0.7399	0.7611	0.8209	0.5389	0.644	0.8282
	Min	1	1	1	6	7	1
	Max	82	76	31	49	58	32
	<i>n</i>	1302			17		
	Median	12	16.51	4	21	21	8
Quartz	Mean	13.72	13.07	5.16	19.33	14	10
	SD	8.469	8.665	4.203	17.62	9	9.9849
	IQR	8	9	4.25	17	9	9.5
	CV	0.6173	0.662	0.814	0.9112	0.6428	9.849
	Min	2	3	1	5	5	2
	Max	50	48	24	39	23	21
	<i>n</i>	220			3		
	Median	11	10	4	14	14	7
Quartzite	Mean	17.81	18.15	5.71	31.77	31.84	9.31
	SD	12.73	12.709	4.729	16.78	17.88	5.79
	IQR	14	14	6	23	24	9
	CV	0.7147	0.7	0.828	0.528	0.5617	0.6223
	Min	2	2	1	7	5	1
	Max	90	102	32	78	90	21
	<i>n</i>	1436			61		
	Median	13	14	4	28	28	8
Neogene							
chert	Mean	16.33	15.4	5.21	35.59	31.84	10.93
	SD	12.278	11.559	4.682	22.91	22.34	7.47
	IQR	12	13	5			
	CV	0.751	0.7505	0.899	0.6438	0.7017	0.6831
	Min	1	1	0	3	1	1
	Max	150	89	45	93	102	34
	<i>n</i>	3265			61		
	Median	13	12	4	29	26	9
Cretaceous							
chert	Mean	14.81	14.27	4.31	29.76	24	8.18
	SD	9.37	8.332	3.373	14.84	9.64	4.2
	IQR	10	10	4			
	CV	0.632	0.583	0.783	0.4987	0.4016	0.5139
	Min	2	1	1	10	3	1
	Max	62	55	25	59	46	17
	<i>n</i>	796			17		

Median	12	12	3	27	23	8
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Abbreviations: CV = coefficient of variation; IQR = interquartile range.

SOM Table S4

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the length, width, and thickness of the complete flakes from the lithic assemblages.

		L. TD10.1			Upper TD10.1-A		
		Length	Width	Thickness	Length	Width	Thickness
Neogene chert	D	0.15562	0.15765	0.20206	0.12157	0.14994	0.12819
	<i>p</i>	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	0.02545	0.0016	0.01422
Cretaceous chert	D	0.14954	0.12464	0.19464	0.93081	0.97012	0.93129
	<i>p</i>	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	0.2246	0.8205	0.02287
Quartzite	D	0.16758	0.14745	0.19537	0.1135	0.13105	0.099421
	<i>p</i>	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	0.04899	0.01093	0.1407
Quartz	D	0.17584	0.17653	0.22007	0.93126	1	0.93041
	<i>p</i>	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	0.4933	1	0.4902
Sandstone	D	0.16957	0.1774	0.20931	0.092393	0.87689	0.79171
	<i>p</i>	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	2.2e-16	0.1721	0.02832	0.001856

SOM Table S5

Length of cutting edge (mm) per kilogram related raw materials.

	Gran Dolina TD10								Galería Complex						
	Upper TD10.1		Lower TD10.1		TD10-2		TD10		GIII		GII		Galería Complex		
	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	
Neogene chert	2391	2391	1824	1824	4088	4088	3392	3392	1746	1746	1260	1260	1658	1658	
Cretaceous chert	4986	4986	3870	3870	8276	8585	6042	6182	2127	2127	4344	4344	3934	3934	
Quartzite	1232	2634	467	1331	811	—	867	1950	472	998	452	1067	463	1053	
Quartz	565	565	—	—	—	—	1302	1302	—	—	—	—	1469	2008	
Sandstone	1299	1645	—	—	—	—	1423	1709	438	786	591	1210	485	1044	
Limestone	—	—	—	—	—	—	112	458	66	159	159	365	134	312	

Abbreviations: T = Total; T w H-M = without natural Bases.

SOM Table S6

Descriptive statistics and coefficients of variation (CV) for the linear variables and indices related to size of the handaxes and cleavers from Lower TD10.1 and Upper TD10.1A.

		Lower TD10.1	Upper TD10.1A
Length	Mean	93.2	111
	SD	15.85	9.09
	CV	0.17	0.08
Width	Mean	62.48	70.66
	SD	12.47	3.09
	CV	0.2	0.04
Thickness	Mean	33.68	39.66
	SD	8.37	6.94
	CV	0.24	0.17
Distal Length	Mean	56.12	60.66
	SD	17.06	10.33
	CV	0.3	0.17
Distal Width	Mean	46.19	50
	SD	11.68	1.62
	CV	0.25	0.03
Distal Thickness	Mean	18.27	23.33
	SD	7.01	5.31
	CV	0.38	0.22
Base Length	Mean	36.91	50.33
	SD	12.36	9.74
	CV	0.33	0.19
Base Width	Mean	55.76	66.33
	SD	15.27	2.62
	CV	0.27	0.03
Elongation	Mean	1.51	1.56
	SD	0.2	0.07
	CV	0.13	0.04
Refinement	Mean	1.9	1.83
	SD	0.29	0.3
	CV	0.68	0.16
Bordes' Edge Shape	Mean	-1.67	-2.25
	SD	1.11	0.52

CV -0.66 -0.23

SOM Table S7

Metric dimensions of the retouched flakes, excluding large cutting tools.

		TD10.1			Upper TD10.1-A		
		Lentgh	Width	Thickness	Length	Width	Thickness
Sandstone	Mean	54.39	35.91	14.89	55.6	40	14.2
	SD	16.81	11.75	6.93	14.26	16.8	4.15
	IQR	16.75	13.25	8	9	9	2
	CV	0.3090609	0.3271	0.46549	0.2564	0.42019	0.29206
	Min	25	13	4	42	24	10
	Max	135	85	40	79	68	21
	<i>n</i>	80			5		
	Median	50	35	15	50	37	14
	Skewness	16.584	127.497	12.849			
Quartz	Mean	34.96	25.27	13.81	47	39	15
	SD	10.07	8.42	4.49	n/a	n/a	n/a
	IQR	9	9.5	6.5			
	CV	0.2881	0.3331	0.3258			
	Min	15	10	5	47	39	15
	Max	66	47	23	1		
	<i>n</i>	26					
	Median	34	24	13.5	47	39	15
	Skewness	10.404	0.96696	0.30507	n/a	n/a	n/a
Quartzite	Mean	49.09	33.99	15.68	46.28	18.71	15.14
	SD	12.97	10.27	5.703	6.94	13.58	6.82
	IQR	17.25	13	9	10.5	16	7.5
	CV	0.2642	0.30205	0.36376	0.1501	0.3509	0.4502
	Min	20	14	2	40	26	5
	Max	82	80	35	57	64	25
	<i>n</i>	196			7		
	Median	47	34	15	44	35	15
	Skewness	0.3868	0.78676	0.42965	n/a	n/a	n/a
Neogene chert	Mean	46.016	33.11	14.42	45.73	37.73	15.37
	SD	14.28	10.72	6.51	18.33	14.21	8.57
	IQR	17	15	8	16.5	16.5	11
	CV	0.31044	0.32374	0.45157	0.40083	0.37651	0.5577
	Min	15	12	2	22	20	5
	Max	100	50	54	90	72	40
	<i>n</i>	247			19		
	Median	42	32	14	42	34	15
	Skewness	0.9119	0.67861	132.522	n/a	n/a	n/a
Cretaceous chert	Mean	38.24	25.91	12.51	36.8	25	11.8
	SD	12.46	7.384	6.51	15.91	8.12	4.97

IQR	15	10	8	30	12	5
CV	0.3259	0.28495	0.43428	0.4324	0.32496	0.42117
Min	15	12	3	21	16	5
Max	82	50	30	54	35	18
<i>n</i>	104			5		
Median	37	25	12	33	22	13
Skewness	0.75106	0.31974	0.76896	n/a	n/a	n/a

SOM References

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